

CORRELATION OF PARENTS AND STUDENTS' SKILLS: EFFECT TO DISTANCE LEARNING PERFORMANCE OF GRADE 8 STEM STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

This study was written to determine if the parents' and students' skills has an effect to the distance learning performance in TLE of Grade 8 STEM students in Tanauan City Integrated High School for the school year 2020-2021. A descriptive-correlational research design was used to determine the relationship of the parents' and students' skills to the distance learning performance in TLE. A total of 100 Grade 8- STEM students were used as the respondents of the study. Correlation analysis was employed to determine relationship between selected variables pertinent to the study. Frequency distribution, percentages, and mean were used to present and to describe the results of the study. 5-point scale responses were constructed for the instruments coded such that a higher score indicated more positive perception toward the item while a lower score implied more negative perception toward an item. The correlation of the respondents' values and attitudes to the distance learning performance in TLE was found to be not significant. The study also showed the findings that the correlation of the assessed parents' skills to the distance learning performance in TLE of Grade 8-STEM students was not significant. On the other hand, the correlation of the assessed students' skills to the distance learning performance was found to be not significant in some indicators such as in problem-solving, information and communication, critical thinking, and self-discipline yet it was found significant in the time management skill indicator. In conclusion, the hypothesis stated that values and attitudes of the respondents is not significantly related to the distance learning performance in TLE and was therefore sustained. On the other hand, the hypothesis stated that parents' skills have no significant relationship with the distance learning performance in TLE. Also, on students' skills in terms of problem-solving, information and communication, critical thinking, and self-discipline were also not significant. But students' skills in time management was found out to be relevant in the academic performance of the students, which was affirmed by the result when the two variables were correlated for relationship.

Keywords: Distance Learning Performance, Parents' Skills, Students' Skills, TLE